

Colloidal iridium nanoparticles in the oxidation of hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium – A kinetic study

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Abstract : Colloidal iridium nanoparticles were prepared successfully by wet chemical way. The catalytic activity of these colloidal iridium nanoparticles was evaluated following the oxidation of alanine (Ala) by hexacyanoferrate(HCF)(III) in alkaline medium. These nanoparticles show a better catalytic activity than the iridium precursor. Easy recovery of the catalyst from the reaction mixture shows another positive significance.

Keywords : Iridium(0) nanoparticles, HCF, oxidation.

Introduction

Noble metal nanoparticles with high specific catalytic activity is important in modern synthetic organic chemistry during the recent years. However how to reduce their dosage is one of the most existing challenges due to the limited reserves of noble metals. With the improved developments in nanochemistry, it is now possible to prepare soluble analogues of heterogeneous catalysts, materials that might have properties intermediate between those of the bulk metal and single metal-particle (homogeneous) catalysts. In general some reports show that Au, Pd, Pt and Ru nanoparticles used in the oxidation process shows good catalytic activity¹⁻⁴. In the present study an attempt has been made to synthesize colloidal iridium nanoparticles (Ir-nano) by wet chemical reduction method. The catalysis by these iridium nanoparticles was studied kinetically using the oxidation of alanine-hexacyanoferrate(III) redox reaction in alkaline medium.

Experimental

Preparation and characterization of Ir-nano :

The iridium nanoparticles were synthesized by the reduction of hexachloroiridic acid (Merck) with methanol using polyvinylpyrrolidone as protecting agent. For their preparation 3.2×10^{-5} mol H_2IrCl_6 was dissolved in 25 ml of methanol. Then a solution of polyvinylpyr-

rolidone in water (0.222 g) was mixed slowly at room temperature by stirring magnetically. After that 1.6 ml of an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (0.2 M) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring. The solution was heated in oil bath for about 1 h. PVP-stabilized nanoparticles were obtained. These nanoparticles were analyzed by FT-IR, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) techniques.

Figs. (1a, b and c) shows the IR spectra of Ir-nano, precursor iridium and pure PVP respectively. The peaks were identified by comparing with literature value⁵. The peaks under the region 2665 cm^{-1} and 2773 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1b) may be due to precursor iridium but a new band near the frequency 2015 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1a) indicates the formation of Ir(0). The red shift of resonance peak of pure PVP at 1700 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1c) to 1664 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1a) indicates the interaction of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of PVP with Ir-nano. The presence of same peaks at 1500 cm^{-1} , 1461 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-C str, N-H bending) in spectra (Figs. 1a and 1b) shows that these groups do not interact with Ir-nano. The XRD analysis (Fig. 2) shows the presence of very small particles. The diffraction peaks were assigned as correspond to the iridium colloidal particles at 2-theta 39.5 and 47.5 for iridium(0). Analysis of the peaks broadening using the Scherrer equation gives an estimate of particle diameter. The X-ray diffractograms of these me-

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of (a) PVP-stabilized colloidal iridium nanoparticles, (b) pure H_2IrCl_6 and (c) pure PVP.

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of Ir(0) nanoparticles.

tallic particles show broad peaks characterization of materials with a small size. Fig. 3 shows a representative TEM image of iridium colloidal particles. Representative TEM micrographs show that individual Ir(0)-nano particle is similar to spherical. The average particle size was estimated to be around 10 nm.

Kinetic study :

Method :

The kinetic measurements were performed spectrophotometrically at constant ionic strength of 0.50 mol dm^{-3} and at constant temperature $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of reaction mixture at λ_{max} 420 nm corresponding to the

Fig. 3. TEM micrograph of iridium(0) nanoparticles.

$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$. The requisite amount of each reactant was kept at 35 °C to attain thermal equilibrium. An appropriate quantity of reactants was mixed in a 100 ml iodine flask. The progress of reaction was monitored by injecting a solution of alanine into the reaction mixture. It was verified that there is negligible interference from other species present in the reaction mixture at 420 nm wavelength. Repeated spectral scans were recorded as a function of time vs absorbance (Fig. 4). Three distinct peaks due to HCF(III) at 275, 310 and 420 nm and an additional peak at 235 nm due to Ir-nano were recorded^{6,7}. The decrease of peak height with time indicates progress of reaction.

Fig. 4. Spectral change of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ during the reaction between [HCF(III)] and [Ala] at 35 °C in the presence of Ir(0)-nanocatalyst.

Results and discussion

To determine the stoichiometry of the reaction different sets of reaction mixtures containing an excess [HCF(III)] over [Ala] at same concentration of colloidal iridium

nanoparticles, NaOH and at constant ionic strength were allowed to react. This mixture was analyzed by titrating against Ce^{IV} solution using ferroin as redox indicator were allowed to react. The results indicate that two moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) were consumed for one mole of alanine.

The main oxidation product keto acid was identified with *o*-hydroxydiphenyl and sulphuric acid by spot test⁸. The product was also characterized by spectroscopic and chromatographic methods (77% ethanol was used). The IR spectrum of the compound revealed the presence of keto acid at ν 1600 cm^{-1} . It was observed that, the products do not undergo further oxidation under the experimental condition.

Effect of [reactant] and medium conditions :

To study the catalytic effect of Ir-nano, the effect of concentration and medium like : Ir-nano, alanine, HCF(III), NaOH and ionic strength are studied on the reaction rate. The data are presented in Table 1.

The effect of substrate concentration was studied by varying its concentration in the range of 1×10^{-3} to 5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} at 35 °C temperature, keeping all other reactants concentrations and conditions constant. The order of reaction was found to be pseudo-first order with respect to lower concentration of alanine. At higher concentration of alanine reaction tends to follow zero order kinetics.

To study the effect of HCF(III) concentration on rate of oxidation, the concentration of HCF(III) was varied from 1×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} at 35 °C at constant [Ala], [Ir-nano], $[\text{OH}^-]$ and ionic strength. The data presented in Table 1 show that with the increase of [HCF(III)] the reaction rate increases linearly showing the first order kinetics with respect to [HCF(III)].

The effect of NaOH concentration on the rate of oxidation was studied by varying the [NaOH] from 0.1 to 0.4 mol dm^{-3} . The increase in reaction rate with the increase of [NaOH] reveals the first order with respect to [NaOH] (Table 1).

The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the $[\mu]$ from 0.2 to 0.5 mol dm^{-3} at constant concentrations of HCF(III), alanine and Ir-nano. The straight line plot shows positive salt effect.

The effect of Ir-nano concentration on the rate of oxidation of alanine has been studied by varying its concentration from 1.23×10^{-6} to 6.14×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} . The study shows that reaction rate increases from 0.9×10^{-3}

Table 1. Effect of variation of [HCF(III)], [Ala], [OH⁻] and [Ir-nano] on reaction rate

[HCF(III)] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ala] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ir-nano] × 10 ⁻⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	(dA/dt) × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)
1	3.0	0.4	1.23	0.5
2	3.0	0.4	1.23	0.9
3	3.0	0.4	1.23	1.2
4	3.0	0.4	1.23	1.6
5	3.0	0.4	1.23	2.1
3	1.0	0.4	1.23	0.7
3	2.0	0.4	1.23	1.0
3	3.0	0.4	1.23	1.3
3	4.0	0.4	1.23	1.6
3	5.0	0.4	1.23	1.6
3	3.0	0.1	1.23	0.5
3	3.0	0.2	1.23	1.0
3	3.0	0.3	1.23	1.5
3	3.0	0.4	1.23	2.0
3	3.0	0.4	1.23	0.9
3	3.0	0.4	2.46	1.4
3	3.0	0.4	3.68	1.6
3	3.0	0.4	4.91	2.0
3	3.0	0.4	6.14	2.5

to $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to [Ir-nano].

A comparison of the data presented in Table 2 shows that reaction rate becomes about two to three times with Ir-nano than with precursor Ir. Thus reduces the dosage of iridium metal.

The Ir-nano used in the reaction mixture were recovered by centrifugation and analyzed by XRD.

Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction :

The effect of temperature on the oxidation of alanine with alkaline HCF(III) has been studied in the presence of Ir-nano catalyst at four temperatures (30, 35, 40 and 45 °C) to evaluate the thermodynamic parameter. The energy of activation was calculated from the slope of the curve as well as application of Arrhenius equation. The value of

different parameters like energy of activation (E_a), enthalpy of formation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔF^\ddagger) are 12.5, 11.88 kcal mol⁻¹, -27.95 e.u and 20.55 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively.

Mechanism :

Based on the above results and previous evidences^{9,10}, following mechanism can be proposed for the oxidation of above said amino acid. It is reported that in alkaline medium anion is the reactive species of amino acids. In the first equilibrium step anion of alanine reacts reversibly with iridium nanoparticles Ir(0) to forms a loosely bonded complex C₁. In the next step the complex C₁ then combines with HCF(III) through electron abstraction to form complex C₂. This C₂ complex slowly disproportionate through a slow step into the final product - keto

Table 2. Effect of [precursor iridium] and [Ir(0)-nano] on the rate of oxidation of alanine

[HCF(III)] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ala] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ir(0)-nano]/[precursor iridium] × 10 ⁻⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	(dA/dt) × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)	
				Ir(0)-nano	Precursor iridium
3	3.0	0.4	1.23	0.9	0.3
3	3.0	0.4	2.46	1.4	0.5
3	3.0	0.4	3.68	1.6	0.7
3	3.0	0.4	4.91	2.0	1.0
3	3.0	0.4	6.14	2.5	1.2

tively at 35 °C. The constancy in k , K_1 and K_2 values and straight line plots support the proposed mechanism and derived rate law.

Conclusion :

Thus from the above study it can be concluded that the reaction occurs through single electron transfer mechanism. The reaction rate using iridium nanoparticles is much higher than the precursor iridium. It may be due to small particle size which provides large surface area. The study also reveals that Ir-nano reduces the dosage of noble metal Ir in such type of reactions.

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